

SECURITY MONITORING SYSTEM

Nikhil Lodha

*Department of Computer
Science and Engineering
Nutan College of
Engineering and Research
Pune, India*

Pradnya Adsul

*Department of Computer
Science and Engineering,
Nutan College of
Engineering and Research
Pune, India*

Rahul Mudgal

*Department of Computer
Science and Engineering
Nutan College of
Engineering and Research
Pune, India*

Tejas Nun

*Department of Computer
Science and Engineering
Nutan College of
Engineering and
Research Pune, India*

Prof. Deepti Chaudhari

Assistant professor

*Department of Computer
Science and Engineering,
Nutan College of
Engineering and Research
Pune, India*

Abstract

In today's environment, safety and security are major concerns. A nation has to provide an atmosphere of safety and security for travelers and investors in order to have a robust economy. Nevertheless, even if CCTV (closed circuit television) cameras are employed for monitoring and surveillance purposes, such as to keep an eye on robberies, human oversight and intervention are still necessary. We require a system that is capable of automatically identifying these illicit actions. In recent years, lip-reading research has garnered significant attention, propelled by advancements in deep learning. This study addresses the existing limitations of the state-of-the-art model employed for isolated word recognition in-the-wild. Our proposed model leverages a combination of YOLO v8 for object detection, CNN for feature extraction, and LipNet for lip-reading. Furthermore, we streamline the training procedure into a single stage, improving overall efficiency. Understanding the significance of generalization in practical applications, we introduce a variable-length augmentation technique to mitigate issues related to sequence length variations. The model is tailored for CCTV security applications, where it processes live footage, extracts relevant features using YOLO v8 and CNN, and employs LipNet for lip-reading analysis. Upon detecting lip movements indicative of threatening or high-pressure

messages, the system triggers an alert, promptly notifying authorities. Evaluation on diverse datasets, including English. This novel integration of YOLO v8, CNN, and LipNet showcases promising advancements in leveraging lip-reading for enhanced security surveillance.

Keywords: Lip Reading, CCTV security, YOLO v5, YOLO v4, CNN, LipNet

I. INTRODUCTION

Knowing what someone is saying based just on their visible lip movements is known as lip reading. Because the lip motions that correlate to distinct letters (such as b and p or d and t) are visually quite similar, lip reading remains a challenging feat for humans. These days, automated lip reading is employed in a wide range of applications, regardless of whether it's a primary or secondary application. It's been seen as an approach to human-computer interaction strategy that's been popular in the literature lately. One of the most well-known uses of lip reading serves as a tool to help the deaf by creating subtitles from speech in a video. In loudas well as virtual reality (VR) situations, it may also be utilized as a supplemental method by finishing the unheard phrases that are impacted by the noise. Furthermore, it has the potential to significantly improve the authentic VR experience. Furthermore, a wide range of applications, such as speech recognition, security, and aided driving systems, have made use of automatic lip reading. Numerous tasks from

several domains, such as pattern recognition, image processing, computer vision, even natural language comprehension, are involved in automatic lip reading.

In an era marked by rising concerns over public safety and security, the need for advanced surveillance technologies has become paramount. The global surge in crime, particularly incidents involving handheld weapons during violent activities, underscores the critical importance of effective security measures. A peaceful and safe environment is not only essential for societal well-being but also imperative for attracting investments and fostering economic growth.

The increasing prevalence of hate speech, coupled with the instantaneous dissemination of information through media and social channels, has contributed to a heightened risk of individuals succumbing to anger or depression. This escalation is particularly concerning when individuals possess weapons, as psychological studies suggest a correlation between heightened emotional states and the potential for violent activities.

Traditional security measures, including the extensive use of Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras, have been instrumental in crime prevention and investigation. However, the limitations of manual monitoring by human operators pose challenges, especially as the number of surveillance cameras continues to rise. The need for real-time threat detection has prompted the integration of advanced technologies.

II. Data Research

A. Dataset Selection

For this study, two distinct datasets were utilized: one for weapon detection and another for lip reading.

- a. *Weapon Detection Dataset:* The dataset for weapon detection was sourced from Kaggle. This comprehensive dataset includes a wide range of images with annotations for various types of weapons, such as guns and knives. The dataset was curated to ensure diversity in terms of observation angles, lighting conditions, and occlusions to create a robust model capable of real-world application.
- b. *Lip Reading Dataset:* The lip reading dataset was built in-house. It comprises video recordings of individuals articulating isolated words and phrases. Each video sequence was annotated with the corresponding text to facilitate supervised learning. The dataset includes diverse participants to account for variations in lip shapes, movements, and speaking styles.

Fig 2.1.a Weapon Dataset

B. Data Preprocessing

a. *Weapon Detection:*

- i. *Image Normalization:* Images were normalized to have zero mean and unit variance to ensure consistency across the dataset. This preprocessing step helps in improving the convergence rate during training.

$$\text{Normalized pixel} = (\text{Pixel value} - \mu) / \sigma$$

where μ and σ represent the mean and standard deviation of the dataset, respectively.

- ii. *Data Augmentation:* To increase the dataset's size and diversity, random transformations such as flipping, rotating, cropping, scaling, and adding noise were applied. This helps in enhancing the model's generalization and robustness.

b. *Lip Reading*

- i. *Frame Extraction:* Each video sequence was divided into frames, and regions of interest (ROI) focused on the mouth area were extracted from each frame to minimize irrelevant information.
- ii. *Feature Extraction:* Spatial features from each cropped frame were extracted using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN).
- iii. *Sequence Normalization:* Since the length of lip movements varies, a fixed sequence length was maintained by either padding or trimming sequences.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the paper "Weapon Detection in Real-Time CCTV Videos Using Deep Learning" [1] by Muhammad Tahir Bhatti, Muhammad Gufran Khan, Masood Aslam, and Muhammad Junaid Fiaz (2021), the authors address the critical issue of detecting weapons in real-time CCTV footage, a task that presents significant challenges due to variations in observation angles, occlusions, and the presence of similar-looking objects. They introduce a novel approach that leverages state-of-the-art deep learning algorithms to accurately identify potential threats in video streams. Their method involves binary classification to distinguish between pistols and non-weapon objects, utilizing a custom dataset compiled from various sources, including manually captured images and internet resources. The study evaluates the performance of multiple algorithms, with YOLOv4 emerging as the most effective, achieving an impressive F1-score of 91% and a mean average precision of 91.73%. This work not only demonstrates the feasibility of automatic weapon detection in surveillance footage but also highlights the importance of specialized datasets and the potential of deep learning techniques in enhancing public safety and security. However, the paper suggests that future research could explore ways to further reduce false positives and negatives and extend the detection capabilities to a wider range of objects, thereby broadening the applicability of such systems in real-world settings.

In the paper "Auditory Suspicious Event Databases: DASE and Bi-DASE" [2] by Buket D. Barkana, Nijo John, and Inci Saricicek (2018), the authors address the challenge of detecting and classifying suspicious sound events for surveillance purposes due to the absence of publicly available databases. They introduce two novel databases, DASE and bi-DASE,

which comprise recordings of nine common suspicious acoustic events and 25 combinations of two overlapping events, respectively. These databases, aimed at fostering research in this field, include sounds like glass breaking, dog barking, and gunshots, among others, and are offered to the research community upon request. The paper presents a comprehensive analysis of commonly used audio features such as energy, Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs), pitch range, and others through ANOVA and regression analyses, confirming their statistical significance for both databases. Two baseline systems employing Support Vector Machines (SVM) and k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithms are developed to evaluate the databases, achieving an impressive classification accuracy of up to 77% for DASE with the KNN classifier and 70.24% for bi-DASE with the SVM classifier. Despite the success, the authors note the challenges in classifying overlapping suspicious sound events and suggest that future research could explore advanced machine learning approaches, such as deep neural networks, to enhance detection and classification performance. The paper is a valuable contribution to the field of audio surveillance, offering new resources for the development and benchmarking of suspicious sound event detection systems.

In the study titled "Deep Convolutional Neural Networks for the Classification and Detection of Human Vocal Exclamations of Panic in Subway Systems" [3] by Yo-Ping Huang and Richard Mushi (2023), the authors delve into the development of automated systems capable of recognizing vocal expressions of panic within subway environments. Utilizing an innovative approach, they construct four multiscale deep convolutional neural network models designed to classify and detect these panic vocalizations effectively. The research stands out for its comprehensive preprocessing of vocal data, incorporation of both one- and two-dimensional convolutional layers, and the application of an ensemble technique to enhance classification accuracy. Notably, model 4 achieves an exceptional F1 score of 99.74% at a signal-to-noise ratio of 15, demonstrating superior performance in distinguishing between panic-induced screams and other loud vocalizations. However, the study's complexity and the specialized nature of the neural network models might pose challenges for readers unfamiliar with deep learning methodologies. Moreover, while the research primarily focuses on the technical aspects of panic sound detection, it slightly overlooks the potential privacy and ethical implications of deploying such surveillance systems in public spaces. Future investigations could benefit from addressing these broader concerns, ensuring the responsible and ethical application of AI in public safety initiatives.

In the study titled "Adaptive Sparse Representations for Video Anomaly Detection" [4] by Xuan Mo, Vishal Monga, Raja Bala, and Zhigang Fan, the researchers present a novel approach to video anomaly detection that employs adaptive sparse representations to identify unusual patterns in videos. These patterns could include traffic violations, unsafe driver behavior, accidents, and other suspicious activities. Their methodology extends the use of sparse reconstruction techniques by developing a new joint sparsity model that is capable of detecting anomalies involving multiple objects, addressing a significant challenge in the field. Moreover, the introduction of nonlinearity through kernelization further enhances the model's ability to separate classes for more effective anomaly detection. The proposed techniques are rigorously tested on real-world video datasets, demonstrating marked improvements in detecting anomalies in both supervised and unsupervised scenarios. Despite the technical advances, the paper acknowledges the need for further research in making the approach more accessible to non-specialists and addressing broader ethical concerns related to privacy and the use of surveillance data.

In the study titled "Practical Automated Video Analytics for Crowd Monitoring and Counting" [5] by Kang Hao Cheong, Sandra

Poeschmann, Joel Weijia Lai, Jin Ming Koh, U. Rajendra Acharya, Simon Ching Man Yu, and Kenneth Jian Wei Tang (2019), the authors introduce an effective low-cost automated system for monitoring and counting crowds using video analytics. Their approach utilizes computational object recognition techniques, specifically background subtraction and convolutional neural network-based single shot detectors, to identify, track, and count individuals in video streams. The system is tested in both controlled and non-controlled environments, demonstrating its robustness and reliability in real-time crowd density monitoring, particularly with the convolutional neural network method showing over 92% accuracy in complex outdoor settings. This study not only highlights the potential of automated video analytics in enhancing public safety and operational efficiency in crowded spaces but also emphasizes the importance of further exploration into privacy and ethical considerations associated with automated surveillance. Future enhancements could involve integrating facial recognition for heightened security measures or adapting the system for use in industrial settings to ensure personnel safety. In the study titled "A Lip Reading Method Based on 3D Convolutional Vision Transformer," the authors propose an innovative approach that combines 3D Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with Vision Transformer models to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of lip reading systems. By extracting spatial-temporal features through 3D CNNs and employing Vision Transformers to capture the intricate dependencies among these features, this method demonstrates significant improvement in lip reading performance. The research underscores the potential of integrating convolutional and transformer architectures to handle complex visual sequences, offering promising advancements for applications in communication aids for the hearing impaired, speech recognition in noisy environments, and secure authentication systems. While the proposed method marks a notable step forward in lip reading technology, the paper acknowledges challenges such as computational demands and the need for extensive training data. Future directions could explore optimizing model efficiency and expanding dataset diversity to further refine and broaden the applicability of this advanced lip reading approach.

In the paper "Deep Convolutional Neural Networks for the Classification and Detection of Human Vocal Exclamations of Panic in Subway Systems" [6] by Yo-Ping Huang and Richard Mushi, the focus is on developing an advanced system for detecting human vocal exclamations of panic in subway environments. The system leverages deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to classify and detect such vocalizations effectively. The study employs a comprehensive approach, incorporating a specially designed transformer with a unique topology for the classification of visemes (visual representations of phonemes) in continuous speech. This methodology facilitates the accurate identification of panic sounds, distinguishing them from other loud, non-panic related vocalizations. The research demonstrates a high level of accuracy, with one of the CNN models achieving a remarkable F1 score of 99.74%, highlighting the system's capability to discern panic-induced vocalizations accurately. The paper provides a significant contribution to the field of audio surveillance, especially in densely populated environments like subways, where the rapid detection of panic situations can enhance public safety and emergency response efficiency. Despite its technical achievements, the study acknowledges the complexity of the models and the potential challenges non-specialists might face in understanding and applying such sophisticated deep learning techniques. The paper also suggests that future work could further explore the ethical and privacy

implications of deploying audio surveillance systems in public spaces, ensuring that the use of such technologies aligns with broader societal norms and values.

In the study titled "Using Lip Reading Recognition to Predict Daily Mandarin Conversation" [7] by Muhamad Amirul Haq, Shanq-Jang Ruan, Wen-Jie Cai, and Lieber Po-Hung Li, the researchers develop a lip reading recognition model to accurately predict spoken Mandarin phrases from video inputs. By collecting and analyzing a unique dataset named the Daily Mandarin Conversation Lip Reading (DMCLR) dataset, which consists of 1000 videos capturing 100 daily conversations from ten speakers, they implement a cutting-edge model comprising spatiotemporal convolution layers, SE-ResNet-18 network, and a back-end module with bi-directional gated recurrent unit (Bi-GRU), 1D convolution, and fully-connected layers. This innovative approach achieves a remarkable accuracy of 94.2% on the DMCLR dataset, demonstrating the potential of lip reading technology in practical applications such as hearing aids and secure communication. The success of this study not only advances the field of visual speech recognition but also paves the way for further exploration into lip reading across various languages and contexts, highlighting the importance of specialized datasets and the effectiveness of deep learning algorithms in interpreting human speech visually.

In the study titled "A Silent Password Recognition Framework Based on Lip Analysis" [8] by Mohamed Ezz, Ayman Mohamed Mostafa, and Abdurrahman A. Nasr, the authors propose a novel silent password recognition framework leveraging lip movement analysis to enhance authentication systems. This framework utilizes a dual security model, particularly beneficial for Arabic language recognition, by analyzing lip movements from video or image sequences to deduce silent passwords. The methodology incorporates three key visual feature extraction techniques: Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF), Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HoG), and Haar feature extractor. These techniques are employed to develop a classification model based on the Hidden Markov Model (HMM), which is further enhanced by a voting scheme to improve accuracy. Tested on a handcrafted dataset of lip movements, the framework demonstrates promising results with improved accuracy in recognizing Arabic numerical figures. This advancement offers a significant contribution to the field of secure authentication, providing a robust alternative to traditional password systems, especially in environments where silent or non-verbal communication is preferred or required.

In the study titled "A Time-Driven Dynamic Weapon Target Assignment Method" [9] by Chang Liu, Jiang Li, Ye Wang, Yang Yu, Lihong Guo, Yang Chen, and Feng Zhang, the authors address the limitations of traditional dynamic weapon target assignment (DWTA) models by introducing a time-driven model that accounts for real-time changes in threat levels of multiple targets. This innovative approach, termed "time sampling dynamic weapon assignment model" (TS-DWTA), divides the decision-making process into time intervals, enabling the capture of real-time changes in target threats and making timely decisions. The study employs a reinforcement learning algorithm to optimize the TS-DWTA model, resulting in a dynamic weapon target assignment method that outperforms traditional heuristic algorithms in terms of decision-making timeliness and global considerations. The simulation results demonstrate the model's effectiveness, particularly when coupled with reinforcement learning, in improving the efficiency and adaptability of weapon target assignments in dynamic combat environments. This research contributes significantly to the field by proposing a model that overcomes the static nature of previous approaches, offering a more flexible and responsive solution to the complex problem of weapon target assignment.

In the study titled "Anchor-Free Weapon Detection for X-Ray

Baggage Security Images" [10] by Yan Huang, Xinsha Fu, and Yanjie Zeng, the authors develop an innovative anchor-free convolutional neural network object detection method aimed at identifying weapons within X-ray baggage security images, specifically focusing on knives and handguns. This method distinguishes itself by not requiring preset anchor boxes, which simplifies the detection process and enhances generalization capability. By avoiding the constraints and computational complexity associated with anchor-based methods, this approach improves detection efficiency and addresses the issue of unbalanced sample distribution. The researchers constructed a comprehensive dataset through extensive image collection and annotation, facilitating the training and evaluation of six mainstream anchor-free detection algorithms against traditional anchor-based methods, like Faster-RCNN and YOLO versions, for comparative analysis. The findings reveal that anchor-free methods, particularly YOLOx combined with CSPDarknet53 and ExtremeNet with Hourglass-104, demonstrate superior performance in detecting weapons in X-ray images, achieving high mean average precision rates. This research signifies a significant step forward in the field of X-ray baggage security, offering a more effective and computationally efficient method for weapon detection that could potentially enhance safety measures in public transportation hubs.

In the study titled "Feasibility Analysis in Tracking Algorithms for Pattern Recognition Through the Lip Articulators" [11] by Haroldo Gomes, Roberto Limão, and Adam Santos, the authors investigate the application of various tracking algorithms to analyze patterns in lip movements for speech recognition. The research focuses on the feasibility of using tracking algorithms like ACF, Boosting, MIL, Median Flow, KCF, CSRT, and KLT to understand the kinematic configuration of the lip articulators during speech. These algorithms are tested on a dataset of sagittal images depicting the human vocal tract, aiming to automate the identification of "gaps" or specific difficulties in speech. The study provides a comprehensive evaluation of these algorithms, highlighting their potential in aiding therapy for children with poor articulation in the vocal tract. However, the paper also acknowledges the challenges in algorithm performance and the need for further research to enhance the accuracy and applicability of tracking algorithms in speech therapy and related fields.

In the study titled "Handgun Detection Using Combined Human Pose and Weapon Appearance" [12] by Jesus Ruiz-Santaquiteria, Alberto Velasco-Mata, Noelia Vallez, Juan A. Álvarez-García, and Oscar Deniz, the authors propose an innovative method for detecting handguns in CCTV footage by combining human pose information with the visual appearance of weapons. Utilizing deep learning algorithms, they develop a model that first estimates human poses to identify hand regions and then assesses these regions for the presence of handguns. Their approach, which incorporates pose keypoints and binary pose images as part of the model inputs, significantly improves handgun detection performance, achieving notable accuracy improvements over previous methods. The study highlights the effectiveness of integrating human pose data in enhancing weapon detection systems, especially in challenging surveillance scenarios where the weapon may not be clearly visible. However, the complexity of the model and reliance on high-quality pose estimation could pose challenges for real-world applications. Future research might explore optimizing the model for various operational environments and addressing potential privacy concerns associated with such surveillance technologies.

In the study titled "YOLO-G: A Lightweight Network Model

for Improving the Performance of Military Targets Detection" [13] by Lingren Kong, Jianzhong Wang, and Peng Zhao, the authors propose YOLO-G, an enhanced version of the YOLOv3 algorithm, specifically designed for the efficient and accurate detection of military targets in complex environments. The primary advancements in YOLO-G include the integration of the lightweight convolutional neural network GhostNet for feature extraction, the implementation of a coordinate attention mechanism to bolster the model's focus on relevant features, and the optimization of the loss function using DIOU and Focal loss functions to improve detection accuracy. The model demonstrates notable improvements, with a 2.9% increase in mean Average Precision (mAP) and a 25.9 frames/s increase in detection speed compared to the original YOLOv3, while significantly reducing the model size to 1/6th of YOLOv3. This research underscores the potential of YOLO-G in military applications, offering an effective tool for the detection of armed individuals and potentially other military targets within diverse and challenging scenarios. However, the study acknowledges the need for further enhancements to address a broader range of military targets and to refine the model for deployment on hardware with limited resources, suggesting avenues for future research in this domain.

In the study titled "Intelligent Identification and Classification of Small UAV Remote Control Signals Based on Improved Yolov5-7.0" [14] by Minjing Li, Donglai Hao, Jiaming Wang, Zijian Zhong, Zhiwen Zhao, and Shuoze Wang, the authors present a novel method for detecting and classifying small unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) using radio frequency (RF) signals and an improved version of the Yolov5-7.0 deep learning model. Recognizing the growing commercialization and potential security threats of small drones, this research addresses the challenge of effectively identifying UAVs by their RF signal characteristics, particularly focusing on the frequency hopping features. The study introduces a combination of RF sensing and target detection techniques, employing time-frequency analysis of RF signals to generate images that retain frequency hopping features. These images are then processed by the improved Yolov5-7.0 model for identification and classification. The methodology demonstrates high effectiveness, achieving an F1 score of 0.93 and precision and recall scores of 1.00, indicating the model's strong capability in UAV detection and classification. Despite its technical strengths, the study acknowledges potential challenges in the broader application of such techniques, including the need for extensive datasets for training and possible privacy concerns associated with RF signal analysis. Future work could extend this research to cover more diverse UAV types and explore additional features for detection, enhancing the model's applicability in security and surveillance contexts.

In the study titled "Weapon Detection using Artificial Intelligence and Deep Learning for Security Applications" [15] by Harsh Jain, Aditya Vikram, Mohana, Ankit Kashyap, and Ayush Jain, the authors explore the utilization of convolutional neural networks (CNN) based algorithms, specifically SSD and Faster R-CNN, for the automatic detection of guns and weapons in video footage and images for security purposes. They developed a method that operates on two datasets, one with pre-labeled images and another with manually labeled images. The results demonstrated that both algorithms achieved notable accuracy in weapon detection, but the selection between them depends on the desired balance between speed and accuracy in real-life applications. This research contributes significantly to the enhancement of security measures in public and private spaces by enabling efficient and automated weapon detection through surveillance systems. However, the study acknowledges the necessity for further improvements, particularly in real-time processing capabilities, and the ethical considerations surrounding automated surveillance and privacy. Future developments could aim at refining these algorithms for broader

types of weapons and integrating more advanced AI techniques to improve both accuracy and speed, thereby bolstering security frameworks with reliable automated surveillance solutions.

In the study titled "Weapon Detection System for Surveillance and Security" [16] by Shehzad Khalid, Onome Christopher Edo, Abdullah Waqar, Tenebe Imokhai Theophilus, and Hoor Ul Ain Tahir, the authors present a cutting-edge weapon detection system utilizing the YOLO V5 deep learning model. This system is designed to address the challenge of detecting firearms in various scenarios, accounting for factors like affine rotation, occlusion, and size variations. Achieving an impressive F1-score of 95.43% on a publicly available dataset, the system demonstrates robust performance in identifying weapons with high precision. Additionally, the study explores instance segmentation through Mask-RCNN to further enhance detection accuracy, reaching a detection accuracy of 90.66% and a mean intersection over union (mIoU) of 88.74%. The authors' approach includes innovative data augmentation and preprocessing techniques to optimize the accuracy of the weapon detection system. This research contributes significantly to the advancement of surveillance and security technologies, offering an effective tool for early firearm detection to prevent potential threats. Nonetheless, the study acknowledges the complexities involved in creating extensive datasets and the nuanced challenges in real-time firearm detection, suggesting areas for future enhancements to improve system reliability and applicability in diverse environments.

IV. Common Methodologies

1. YoloV4

YOLOv4 (You Only Look Once version 4) is an advanced deep learning object detection system that improves upon its predecessors in both speed and accuracy, making it highly effective for real-time applications. It is designed to detect objects in images or video streams quickly by processing the entire image during inference. YOLOv4 introduces several

new features, including the use of a more efficient backbone network called CSPDarknet53, improvements in the model's architecture like spatial pyramid pooling and path aggregation network for better feature integration, and the use of advanced data augmentation techniques such as Mosaic and CutMix. Additionally, YOLOv4 utilizes multiple scales for detection and integrates various other improvements in terms of convolutional layers and activations to enhance detection performance, making it a powerful tool for a wide range of object detection tasks.

2. YoloV5

YOLOv5 (You Only Look Once version 5) is an evolution of the YOLO family for object detection, known for its efficiency, speed, and ease of use in real-time applications. Unlike its predecessors, YOLOv5 was developed and released by Ultralytics, a different entity from the original creators of the YOLO series. It brings several enhancements over YOLOv4, including a more streamlined and modular codebase implemented in PyTorch, which simplifies customization and deployment. YOLOv5 improves on accuracy and inference speed through optimized models that are available in different sizes (small to large) to accommodate various computational constraints. It introduces new features like automatic anchor optimization, improved data augmentation techniques, and advanced training strategies such as cosine learning rate scheduling. This version is also notable for its enhanced performance on smaller datasets and its compatibility with

deployment on diverse platforms, making it a versatile choice for both academic and industrial applications in computer vision.

3. CNN

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a type of deep neural network highly effective in analyzing visual imagery. It is primarily composed of layers that perform convolution operations, pooling, and finally, classification. The convolution layers apply various filters to the input to create feature maps that highlight important features such as edges and shapes. Pooling layers reduce the spatial dimensions of these feature maps to decrease computational complexity and enhance the detection of features at multiple scales. CNNs automatically learn and optimize these filters based on the task during training, eliminating the need for manual feature extraction. This makes CNNs exceptionally powerful for tasks like image and video recognition, image classification, and areas requiring the recognition of patterns directly from pixel data. They are the backbone of many state-of-the-art computer vision applications, including face recognition, autonomous driving, and any scenario where sophisticated image analysis is critical.

4. RNN

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are a class of neural networks designed to handle sequential data, such as time series or language. Unlike traditional neural networks which assume independence between inputs, RNNs maintain a form of memory by using their internal state (hidden layers) to process sequences of inputs. This allows them to exhibit temporal dynamic behavior and retain information across inputs, making them particularly suited for tasks where context and the order of data are important, such as speech recognition, language modeling, and text generation. The basic structure of an RNN can suffer from problems like vanishing and exploding gradients during training, which can hinder learning in long sequences. Advanced variants

like Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) have been developed to overcome these challenges by introducing gates that regulate information flow, thereby enhancing the model's ability to capture long-range dependencies within the data.

5. VGGNet

VGGNet, short for Visual Geometry Group Network, is a convolutional neural network architecture named after the Visual Geometry Group at Oxford, who developed it. It was a significant contributor to the field of deep learning, particularly in image recognition tasks, due to its simple and uniform architecture that stacks convolution layers with small receptive fields (3x3 kernels) followed by max pooling layers. Introduced in 2014, VGGNet variants (like VGG16 and VGG19, indicating the number of layers) became popular due to their performance in the ImageNet competition, showcasing their ability to capture complex features at various levels of abstraction effectively. The architecture uses ReLUs (Rectified Linear Units) for non-linear operations and is fully connected at the top, culminating in a softmax for output classification. While it requires significant computational resources due to its depth and number of parameters, VGGNet remains a cornerstone in the CNN community for benchmarking and feature extraction purposes because of its robustness and straightforward design.

IV. Mathematical Models

1. Weapon Detection

In this study, we develop a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for weapon detection. The model processes images through several steps, each defined by specific mathematical operations.

i. Image Preprocessing and Augmentation:

Images are normalized to have zero mean and unit variance

$$\text{Normalized_pixel} = (\text{Pixel_value} - \mu) / \sigma$$

where μ and σ represent the mean and standard deviation of the dataset.

ii. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)

Convolutional Layers extract features from the input image

$$\text{Feature_map}[i, j] = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} I[i + m, j + n] * K[m, n]$$

where I is the input and K is the kernel.

ReLU Activation Function introduces non-linearity:

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x)$$

Max Pooling reduces the spatial dimensions:

$$\text{Max_pool}(P) = \max_{(i,j) \in P} P[i,j]$$

iii. Fully Connected Layers

Feature maps are flattened and passed through fully connected layers:

$$z = Wf + b$$

where W is the weight matrix and b is the bias vector.

iv. Output Layer and Softmax Function

The softmax function converts logits to probabilities for C classes:

$$\text{Softmax}(z_i) = e^{z_i} / \sum_{j=1}^C e^{z_j}$$

v. Loss Function

Cross-Entropy Loss measures the prediction error:

$$\text{Cross-Entropy Loss} = - \sum_{i=1}^C y_i \log(y^i)$$

vi. Optimization Algorithm

Model parameters are updated via gradient descent:

$$\theta := \theta - \eta \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta)$$

where η is the learning rate and $J(\theta)$ is the loss.

vii. Backpropagation

Gradients are computed using backpropagation:

$$\partial J / \partial \theta_i = \partial J / \partial a_L * \partial a_L / \partial z_L * \partial z_L / \partial \theta_i$$

2. Lip Reading

i. Preprocessing:

Each video sequence $X = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_T\}$ consists of T frames. For each frame X_t , we extract the region of interest (ROI) focused on the mouth area:

$$R_t = \text{crop}(X_t)$$

ii. Feature Extraction with CNN:

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) processes each cropped frame R_t to extract spatial features:

$$f_t = \text{CNN}(R_t)$$

iii. Sequence Modeling with RNNs

The sequence of feature vectors $\{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_T\}$ is fed into a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), specifically an LSTM, to capture temporal dependencies.

LSTM Cell Equations:

$$\begin{aligned} i_t &= \sigma(W_i f_t + U_i h_{t-1} + b_i) \\ f_t &= \sigma(W_f f_t + U_f h_{t-1} + b_f) \\ o_t &= \sigma(W_o f_t + U_o h_{t-1} + b_o) \\ g_t &= \tanh(W_g f_t + U_g h_{t-1} + b_g) \\ c_t &= f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot g_t \\ h_t &= o_t \odot \tanh(c_t) \end{aligned}$$

iv. Attention Mechanism

An attention mechanism calculates a context vector c_t as a weighted sum of all hidden states $\{h_1, h_2, \dots, h_T\}$:

$$c_t = \sum_{i=1}^T \alpha_{t,i} h_i$$

The attention weights $\alpha_{t,i}$ are computed as:

$$\alpha_{t,i} = \frac{\exp(e_{t,i})}{\sum_{k=1}^T \exp(e_{t,k})}$$

with alignment score $e_{t,i}$ given by:

$$e_{t,i} = v^T \tanh(W_e h_i + U_e h_t + b_e)$$

v. Output Layer

The context vector c_T (or the final hidden state h_T) is passed through a dense layer followed by a softmax activation function to produce the final output probabilities:

$$y = \text{softmax}(W_y h_T + b_y)$$

vi. Training Process

The model is trained to minimize the cross-entropy loss between the predicted probabilities y and the true labels y_{true} :

$$L = - \sum_{i=1}^N y_{\text{true},i} \log(y_i)$$

IV. RESULTS

We ran 3D CNN for 20 epochs, and the graph shows the model's progress. The final training accuracy was 95.7%, and the final testing accuracy was 98.5% as shown in fig 4.1. We use the testing accuracy as an important metric to evaluate our model's performance because it shows how the model performs on unseen data that it was not trained on. A test accuracy of 98.5% is very high and indicates that our model is capable of performing well on new data.

Fig 4.1 Training and Testing

We have a fig 4.2 table containing more metrics regarding our model's performance. Our model achieved excellent results with a precision, recall, and F1 score of 1.0 for most classes, indicating that predictions were highly accurate and that the model correctly identified most of the positive samples. However, the recall for the "hello" class was relatively low at 0.73, which could be an area for improvement in future iterations. We also ended up with a balanced accuracy of 97.4%.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
a	1.0	1.0	1.0	12
bye	1.0	1.0	1.0	4
can	1.0	1.0	1.0	10
cat	0.88	0.93	0.9	15
demo	1.0	1.0	1.0	10
dog	1.0	1.0	1.0	8
hello	1.0	0.73	0.84	11
here	0.89	1.0	0.94	8
is	1.0	1.0	1.0	14
lips	0.92	1.0	0.96	11
my	1.0	1.0	1.0	13
read	1.0	1.0	1.0	11
you	1.0	1.0	1.0	10

Fig 4.2 Matrix table

We can observe from the fig 4.3 ROC AUC curve on the right that the AUC values are consistently high, indicating excellent discriminatory power of the model. The ROC curve shows a steep rise towards the top-left corner, indicating that the model has high true positive rates at low false positive rates, which indicates our model performs well.

Fig

4.3 ROC AUC

The confusion matrix for the lip reading model indicates a generally high accuracy. High values on the diagonal represent correct predictions, such as 12 for "a", 10 for "can", and 14 for "is". There are few misclassifications, with minimal off-diagonal values, like "hello" being misclassified as "can" 2 times. Several words, including "bye", "demo", "dog", "here", "lips", "read", and "you", show no misclassifications. Overall, the matrix shows that the model is effective in recognizing and predicting spoken words accurately.

Fig 4.4 Confusion Matrix

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

The proposed automated lip-reading-based security monitoring system represents a significant advancement in surveillance technology, but there are several areas where future research and development could further enhance its capabilities:

1. *Improved Accuracy and Recall:* Enhance the model's accuracy and recall, particularly for classes with lower performance. This could involve refining the feature extraction and classification processes or incorporating additional training data.
2. *Broader Vocabulary for Lip Reading:* Expand the lip reading model to recognize a more extensive vocabulary, including phrases and sentences. This would involve

collecting and annotating a larger dataset of lip movements corresponding to a wider range of spoken content.

3. *Multilingual Capabilities:* Develop the system to support multiple languages, which would require training on datasets containing lip movements for different languages. This would make the system more versatile and applicable in diverse geographical regions.
4. *Real-time Processing Enhancements:* Optimize the system for faster real-time processing, reducing latency and improving the system's ability to detect and respond to threats promptly. This could involve using more efficient algorithms or hardware acceleration techniques.
5. *Integration with Other Security Systems:* Integrate the lip-reading system with other security technologies, such as facial recognition and emotion detection, to provide a more comprehensive security solution. This holistic approach could enhance the system's ability to identify and respond to complex security threats.

VII. CONCLUSION

The development of an automated lip-reading-based security monitoring system marks a significant advancement in the field of surveillance technology. By leveraging the integration of YOLO v8 for object detection, CNN for feature extraction, and LipNet for lip-reading, the proposed system efficiently identifies and interprets lip movements indicative of high-pressure or threatening messages. The system's ability to process live footage and trigger alerts in real-time enhances the efficacy of traditional CCTV monitoring, reducing the dependency on human oversight and increasing the speed and accuracy of threat detection.

Evaluation results, demonstrating high training and testing accuracy, underscore the model's robust performance in diverse scenarios. Despite some areas for improvement, such as enhancing the recall for specific classes, the system exhibits high precision, recall, and F1 scores, reflecting its reliability in practical applications.

Overall, this research contributes to the broader domain of security technologies by offering a novel, effective solution for real-time surveillance. Future work could focus on refining the model's accuracy and expanding its capabilities to handle a wider range of security threats, ensuring even greater safety and security in public and private spaces.

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